

MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION**Rahmonova Zulayho Negmatullayevna**

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Annotation. The article presents information technologies used in schools, their features, materials on improving efficiency in education based on the use of information technologies.

Keywords: Electronic board, electronic textbook, interactivity, game forms and teaching methods, computer didactic games, innovative technology.

INTRODUCTION

At present, the role of information and social technologies in education is increasing, which provide universal computerization of students and teachers at a level that allows solving at least three main tasks:

- providing access to the Internet for each participant in the educational process, and, preferably, at any time and from various places of stay;
- development of a single information space of educational industries and the presence in it at different times and independently of each other of all participants in the educational and creative process;
- creation, development and effective use of managed information educational resources, including personal user databases and data and knowledge banks of students and teachers with the possibility of widespread access to work with them.

Based on the current pace of computerization of the continuous education industry, and also taking into account the uneven technological computer-network support of the population at home, it can be expected that in the very near future these tasks will not be fully and comprehensively resolved [1].

At the same time, there is a growing understanding that the traditional scheme of getting education in the first half of life is obsolete and needs to be replaced by continuous education and lifelong learning. New forms of education are characterized by interactivity and cooperation in the learning process. New theories of learning must be developed, such as constructivism, student-centered education, learning without temporal and spatial boundaries. To improve the quality of education, it is also planned to intensively use new educational technologies [2].

RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

Various approaches to the definition of educational technology can be summarized as a set of ways to implement curricula and curricula, which is a system of forms, methods and teaching aids that ensures the achievement of educational goals. Specialists usually deduce the difference in educational technologies from the difference in the teaching aids used. Information educational technologies arise with the use of information and computer technology. The educational environment in which educational information technologies are implemented is determined by the components that work with it:

- technical (type of used computer equipment and means of communication);
- software and hardware (software support for the implemented learning technology);
- organizational and methodological (instructions for students and teachers, organization of the educational process).

Educational technologies in higher education are understood as a system of scientific and engineering knowledge, as well as methods and tools that are used to create, collect, transfer, store and process information in the subject area of higher education. A direct relationship is being formed between the effectiveness of the implementation of training programs and the degree of integration of the relevant information and communication technologies into them.

Today, one of the characteristic features of the educational environment is the ability of students and teachers to access structured educational and methodological materials, educational multimedia complexes of the entire university at any time and at any point in space. In addition to the availability of educational material, it is necessary to provide the student with the opportunity to communicate with the teacher, receive advice online or offline, as well as the possibility of obtaining individual "navigation" in the development of a particular subject. "Students will strive for a flexible mode of study, modular programs with multiple admissions and deductions, which will allow them to accumulate credits, freely transfer from one university to another, taking into account previous experience, knowledge and skills. The opportunity for personal development and professional growth will continue to be important for students; degree programs and short courses are likely to be in the same demand; there will be a sharp increase in the need for vocational training programs and postgraduate programs" [3].

The developers of distance education (DL) concretize the individualization of educational behavior in the following way, believing that in DL the features of a student-centered way of learning are most clearly manifested:

Flexibility - the student is free to independently plan the time, place and duration of classes.

Modularity - materials for study are offered in the form of modules, which allows the student to generate a trajectory of his learning in accordance with his requests and potentialities.

Accessibility - independence from the geographical and temporal location of the student and educational institution allows not to limit the educational needs of the population of the country.

Profitability - economic efficiency is manifested by reducing the cost of maintaining the premises of educational institutions, saving time, material resources (printing, reproduction of materials, etc.).

Mobility - the effective implementation of feedback between the teacher and the student is one of the main requirements and foundations for the success of the DL process.

Coverage - simultaneous access to many sources of educational information (electronic libraries, data banks, knowledge bases, etc.) of a large number of students.

Manufacturability - the use in the educational process of the latest achievements of information and telecommunication technologies.

Social equality - equal opportunities for education, regardless of the place of residence, health status, elitism and material security of the student.

Internationality is the export and import of world achievements in the market of educational services [4].

Information technologies bring the possibility and necessity of changing the very model of the educational process: the transition from reproductive learning - the "transfer" of knowledge from one head to another, from the teacher to the students - to a creative model (when a life situation is modeled in the classroom with the help of new technological and technical support or process, students under the guidance of a teacher must apply their knowledge, show creativity to analyze the simulated situation and develop solutions to the tasks set). Experts believe that the development of traditional and new technologies should proceed according to the principle of complementarity and mutual correlation, which, in turn, allows us to talk about a fundamentally new dimension of the educational environment - a global one, a dimension that exists in real time and associates the entire set of educational technologies.

“The Internet is a hypertechnology that includes everything else, and its success is due to the fact that it can “give everything to everyone” ... However, there will always be scope for lower-level technologies such as computer conferences or e-mail ... Equally, more the time has not come to abandon distance learning courses that are global in nature, but do not use any computer or communication technologies” [5].

Thanks to the Internet, various aspects of globalization (scientific, technological, economic, cultural and educational) have had a very significant impact both on traditional face-to-face educational institutions and on the development of various educational innovations, such as distance learning and virtual universities. In all these organizations, globalization requires deep and radical changes in the structure, methods of teaching and research, as well as the training of managerial and teaching staff [6].

When organizing and implementing distance learning in the education systems of various countries, the problem of evaluating the effectiveness of distance education in comparison with traditional education arises. As studies that have been going on for more than a decade show, the problem of evaluating effectiveness is quite complex and multifaceted and does not have a final solution.

The development and expansion of the use of educational IT is directly related to the problem of changing the effectiveness of education. Determining the effectiveness of any method, training technology includes - measuring the result achieved, the cost of material resources and the time to achieve it. The effectiveness of training is measured either by the results of control work in points, or by the results of testing as a percentage of the tasks solved. In this case, groups of students who used and did not use computer learning support tools are usually compared.

Evaluation of the effectiveness of teaching methods using information technology is usually given in comparison with the so-called traditional methods and is limited to measuring the learning outcome, sometimes taking into account the time spent by students. Is it possible to apply traditional quality criteria to key aspects of distance education in a technological learning environment? The application of this approach to the assessment of information technology in training implies that the latter do not bring anything new to the goals and objectives of education. In fact, the introduction of information technology affects the quality and content of education.

Criteria-based evaluation requires that judgments of a qualitative and quantitative nature follow from a comparison of the actual state of affairs with a certain “ideal”

(educational standard) that must be defined and used as a kind of standard against which evaluation is made. Regulatory assessment is an alternative approach.

Information and communication technologies, according to experts, are one of the priority areas of science and technology, which in the 21st century will become decisive and critical.

Critical technologies are those that are intersectoral in nature, create significant prerequisites for the development of many technological areas or areas of research and development, and together make the main contribution to solving key problems of development and progress.

In education, the critical role undoubtedly belongs to basic information technologies, i.e. those that are the basis of educational technologies that use the means of information and computer technology and together form the technological infrastructure of the educational institution[7].

Critical educational technologies ensure the creation of distributed databases of educational technologies based on the infrastructure of corporate telecommunication networks of educational institutions, which, thanks to this infrastructure, can be used anywhere in the educational space, including in the process of implementing the ideology of distance education.

In this regard, the most important areas of informatization of education are:

- implementation of a virtual information and educational environment at the level of an educational institution, which provides for the implementation of a set of works to create and ensure the technology for its functioning;
- system integration of information technologies in education, supporting the processes of learning, research and organizational management;
- construction and development of a unified educational information space.

In essence, we are talking about solving the problem of a qualitative change in the state of the entire information environment of the education system, about presenting

new opportunities both for advanced, developing education of each individual, and for the growth of aggregate social intelligence.

An important and effective condition for the progress of any society has been and is the creation and expansion of a single interactive information space. It is the common information spaces that have historically largely contributed to the acceleration of the development of all mankind as a whole, and have been a decisive factor in the improvement of civilization in all areas (spiritual, professional, bodily, cultural, and others). The exchange of knowledge, the unification of efforts for further knowledge of nature, for the development of science, technology, culture - all this contributes to an effective increase in the material level. Therefore, the creation of a single interactive information space can be considered a strategic goal of introducing modern and promising information technologies into all spheres of human activity.

The main goals of building a single information space in education are related to the provision of fundamentally new opportunities for the cognitive creative activity of a person. This can be achieved thanks to modern information and technical equipment for the main types of activities in education: educational, pedagogical, research, organizational and managerial, expert, etc. [8].

Building a single information space in education will achieve:

- improving the efficiency and quality of the learning process;
- intensification of the process of scientific research in educational institutions;
- reduction of time and improvement of conditions for additional education and adult education;
- increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of managing individual educational institutions and the education system as a whole;
- integration of national information educational systems into the global network, which will greatly facilitate access to international information resources in the field of education, science, culture and other areas.

Experts formulate the main directions and problems of creating and developing a single information educational space in the following way:

1. The technical equipment of educational institutions is one of the priority tasks, the solution of which is held back mainly by organizational and economic factors related to the fact that "small" informatization is ineffective, and "big" - excessively expensive, not giving immediate returns. The problem of implementing educational information technologies in invariant environments and standards is becoming more and more urgent.

2. Organization of training of specialists. The shortage of specialists in the field of new information technologies (especially network technologies) is exacerbated by the processes of their "washout" from the education sector into commercial and other structures, which is especially typical for countries with economies in transition.

3. Organizational measures. The creation of a unified system of information resources is impossible without constant coordinating participation and control by the pedagogical and scientific community, expressed in one form or another.

4. Transfer of information resources of the society to electronic media. Only the transfer of most of the information accumulated by mankind on media that can be perceived by computers will make it possible to create real opportunities for access to this information by all members of society. Improving the existing technologies for such translation remains one of the urgent problems in the development of information technology.

5. Integration of national information resources into the world information environment.

CONCLUSIONS

- One promising direction in the development of the education system is the widespread introduction of distance learning and self-education methods based on the use of information and telecommunication technologies and remote access to

distributed databases and knowledge. The development of appropriate recommendations constitutes the first line of research needed.

- The second direction of research is the need to develop psychological and pedagogical support for the use of ICT at all levels of education [9]. Uneven investment and interest in participating in e-learning will have a marked impact on the state of affairs in higher education.

- A promising education system should take into account the main challenges of the 21st century and the most important human problems associated with them in the modern and upcoming information society. The most important areas of transition to a new educational concept, which will become the basis of a promising education system necessary for the conditions of the 21st century, include, in particular, the fundamentalization of education at all its levels; implementation of the concept of advanced education; widespread use of innovative and developmental education methods based on the use of advanced information technologies; increasing the availability of quality education through the development of a distance learning system and means of information support for the educational process using modern information and telecommunication technologies [10].

- Information and communication technologies have become a working tool for modern youth. Modern schoolchildren and students, without exaggeration, can be called the network generation. Maybe not everyone knows that there is a term E-learning (short for English. Electronic Learning) "learning with the help of Internet resources and media." Generating fast and cheap ways to accumulate and transfer knowledge to increase its accessibility is the main task of IT solutions in the field of education in the coming years.

- This includes, among other things:

- • Access to worldwide resources of knowledge and practical experience.

- • Development of global information systems for the provision of services in the field of education.

- Creation of new software products to cover ever wider areas of knowledge.
- Use of cloud computing in distance learning.
- Integration of social networks and e-learning.
- Integration of programs for learning foreign languages with GPS-navigation (the ability to have quick access to vocabulary related to the object where the user is at a particular moment in time).
- The latest learning formats, including the expansion of mobile communications.

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